

CULTUROLOGY

FAMILY AND HOUSEHOLD ISSUES, HOLIDAYS, WEDDINGS AND NUPTIALS IN WESTERN AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

The term “ethnography” emerged in the Middle Ages as a field of study that focuses on the people, describing their customs, traditions, everyday life issues, and being more familiar with their desires and aspirations, as well as being closer to them. Therefore, the primary task of ethnography as a scientific discipline is to study the people, their history, ethnography, lifestyle, customs and traditions, wedding and mourning ceremonies, as well as national, religious, and calendar holidays, and to enrich this knowledge further through scientific research.

Although ethnography as a scientific discipline has been practiced since ancient times in the global community, the systematic collection of ethnographic data regarding the life and activities of the peoples living on the territory of Azerbaijan began in the XIX century. Nevertheless, the origin of acquiring ethnographic knowledge about the life and activities of the people living on the lands of Azerbaijan dates back to the ancient and medieval periods.

The article examines the traditions, everyday life issues, ethno-cosmic customs, trials, and the continuation of mythical conceptions in the ritual behavior acts of the modern era in Western Azerbaijan, with analyses conducted on these aspects. The research reveals that the study of historical and cultural heritage rooted in ancient traditions inherently demonstrates the close interconnection of the territories of Western Azerbaijan—such as the city of Iravan, Vedibasar, Zangazur, Daralayaz, Aghbaba, Shorayel, Loru, Pambak, Goycha, Garagoyunlu, and Shamshaddin—with other regions. It has been documented as a historical fact that the customs, traditions, and lifestyle of the Turks living in the Shamshaddin, Garagoyunlu, Dilijan, and Goycha regions were nearly identical to those of the indigenous population of Ganjabasar.

Keywords: household issues, customs and traditions, calendar holidays, family and marital issues, exogamous, endogamous

Introduction. In the Middle Ages, various works written by great and creative figures of the Azerbaijani people on our traditions, as well as epics of heroism and love, contain extensive and detailed information reflecting different aspects of the ethnography of our people. Since ancient times, travelers from the Near East and European countries who visited Azerbaijan have closely studied the lifestyle of the local population, collecting valuable information on their economy, material and spiritual culture, ancient monuments, traditions, and family-marriage relations, which they later published.

The family code holds a central place in the historically developed traditions of the Azerbaijani people. In an Azerbaijani family, while children are obligated to serve their parents based on the established tradition within the family, parents also have three primary responsibilities towards their children: “...to provide upbringing, education, and to arrange their marriage...” [1.page.136].

The main part. In Azerbaijan, exogamous and endogamous marriage traditions, which had been formed since ancient times, coexisted with monogamous and polygamous marriage practices. During the Middle

Ages, family and marriage relations across all territories of the South Caucasus inhabited by Azerbaijanis began to be regulated by Islamic Sharia law, and the religious rules regarding marriage between relatives were reflected in social life. Precisely in accordance with these rules, numerous scientific research studies have discussed the age and norms of marriage, marriage customs, bride abduction, bride selection, matchmaking, engagement, and wedding traditions, as well as the ceremonies, customs, and traditions performed during weddings, providing explanations regarding their social significance.[4,page.11].

However, there is still a need for further research on the unique aspects of pre-wedding preparations in different regions of Azerbaijan, including the meals prepared during engagement and wedding ceremonies, the music played, the songs performed, the dances practiced, and the sports competitions held. Additionally, the rituals associated with the bride’s arrival at her husband’s home, such as the *duvaq (veil)* or *duvaq qapdı (traditional veil-lifting game)* ceremonies, certain aspects of the young couple’s post-wedding life, traditions related to the upbringing of newborns, rituals performed to protect infants from evil forces, and other

customs and traditions remain subjects that require further scholarly exploration. At the same time, alongside the aforementioned customs and traditions, funeral and mourning ceremonies, lamentations of a mourning nature, elegies recited during mourning rituals, memorial feasts, and other unmentioned aspects are considered valuable examples of our nation's rich cultural heritage.

In 1988, despite the existing protests of the Azerbaijani people, the Soviet leadership, led by Mikhail Gorbachov, adopted a criminal stance against the Azerbaijani population of Western Azerbaijan, relying on falsified information provided by Armenian sources. As a result, during the XX century—and particularly starting from November 23 to December 1, 1988—253,000 Azerbaijanis were once again forcibly deported from their historical ancestral lands within the territory of the Armenian SSR, including the city of Irevan, 185 villages, and other settlements. In relation to this deportation, 31,000 homes, personal properties, and the assets of 165 collective farms belonging to our compatriots were plundered. Furthermore, 214 individuals were killed, 1,154 were injured, hundreds of our fellow countrymen were subjected to torture, and the honor of women and girls was violated. At the same time, more than 15,000 Kurds and several thousand Russians were forcibly expelled from the Armenian SSR. Cities, villages, and settlements where our traditions had been practiced for centuries, along with residential homes, were left abandoned. Our historical and architectural monuments, as well as cemeteries, were destroyed.

The people of Western Azerbaijan, despite being deported from their homeland and becoming refugees at various stages of history, never forgot the customs and traditions that belonged to their nation. Currently, regardless of where they live, people who were once residents of that region in Azerbaijan continue to carry out wedding ceremonies that reflect the national values, lifestyle, and mindset of the Western Azerbaijanis, rooted in their past traditions. These customs and traditions are remembered and practiced in the wedding rituals, and they continue to be embraced in the areas where they have settled, demonstrating that they have not forgotten their national identity.

Following the historic victory of the 44-day Patriotic War for Karabakh, which ended on November 8, 2020, the liberation of Karabakh and Eastern Zangazur by our heroic and valiant soldiers brought us one step closer to reclaiming our occupied lands. As a result, the plan for the return of the people of Western Azerbaijan to their ancestral lands gained relevance, and the support of this movement at the level of the Republic of Azerbaijan called on all segments of society to mobilize for this national unity.

The National Leader of the Azerbaijani People, Heydar Aliyev, rightfully stated, "If we are to examine historical facts, I must remind you that the territory of present-day Armenia was once part of Azerbaijan. These lands once belonged to Azerbaijan, but in 1918-1920, they were transferred to Armenia. In short, if we refer to history, we will see that Armenia owes much to Azerbaijan. However, I am saying now that we have never set our sights on the territory of Armenia, nor do

we have any territorial claims against them. At the same time, we cannot agree to give up even one meter of our own land!"[6].

The Western Azerbaijan region, with its rich history, culture, and traditions, is a historically significant part of Azerbaijan. Our compatriots who were subjected to deportation from there have never forgotten their ancestral land. The architecture, folk art, and musical traditions of this region, with deep roots and a unique character, have been shaped over time. The harsh climatic conditions of the mountainous regions, along with hard work, perseverance, patriotism, and loyalty to their language, religion, national and spiritual values, and traditions, are characteristics inherent to the people of Western Azerbaijan. Overall, Western Azerbaijan, including the Irevan region, has historically been a land rich in national, religious, and calendar-based holidays and ceremonies. These holidays and events are ritual practices conducted by the people who have lived in the region for millennia, related to nature and the passage of time. The rituals conducted in the region are considered the historical chronicles of the people who have lived there. These customs and traditions continue to find their place in our modern lives, cherished and embraced.

One of the most significant traditions of the people of Western Azerbaijan, which encompasses many of their spiritual values, is the celebration of Novruz holiday. Regardless of where and under what conditions they have lived, this tradition has endured and reached the present day. The eve and arrival of Novruz, along with the associated customs and traditions, as well as the celebrations of Novruz holiday, were observed on a large scale in the lands of Western Azerbaijan, in accordance with age-old traditions passed down through the centuries. In Irevan, Zangazur, Vedibasir, Basarkechar, Gafan, and other lands of Western Azerbaijan, people would prepare in advance for Novruz holiday and celebrate this traditional holiday with great solemnity in every household. The preparation period for the holiday specifically included special preparations for the great and small Chilles, the four small Chilles, or the preparations for the Gray Month." In these lands, the winter season is divided into Chilles, with the first being the Great Chilla, which began with the onset of winter and lasted for forty days. The second is called the Small Chilla, lasting for twenty days, half the duration of the Great Chilla. Finally, the last month of winter is known as the Gray Month, which ends with four small Chilles, each lasting seven days.

The preparation processes for Novruz by the population living in Western Azerbaijan begin immediately after the end of the winter season. The "third Chilla" covering the month between the small Chilla and Novruz was referred to as the "Gray month" in Western Azerbaijan, while the "four small Chilla" were called "Jamla (The gathering)". It is said that on the final night of the twenty-day small Chilla, people historically referred to it as "the gathering (Jamla) falls to the ground." The meaning of this phrase was interpreted as the earth beginning to breathe and come to life. Following this, it was believed that the gathering (Jamla) would fall into water, fire, and air. During this period,

leading up to the holiday, courtyards and homes would be cleared of bushes and unnecessary items. At the same time, young women would organize and tidy up the household.

In Western Azerbaijan, during the pre-holiday period, all households would conduct the rituals of "house cleaning" or "clothing washing." Families would hang out their bedding and blankets to dry, while cleaning the house, washing the doors and windows, and tidying up the entire household. Since these cleaning tasks were considered the first essential condition for welcoming the holiday, bonfires would be lit separately on each of the four Tuesday evenings leading up to the holiday.

On the final Tuesday evening of the year, it was referred to as "Ilakhir (*The last Tuesday of the year*) Tuesday" across all regions of Western Azerbaijan, and this holiday was celebrated in a special and festive manner. On the day of the Last Tuesday, the villagers would participate in a ceremony known as "qəbirüstü" (cemetery visitation) to honor their ancestors. They would visit the graves of their deceased loved ones and clean the surrounding areas of bushes and debris. In this process, the deceased are visited, religious leaders recite the Yasin (*It is often recited in Islamic traditions, particularly in moments of remembrance for the deceased, seeking blessings and mercy for the departed soul*), and those with vows offer sweets and halva (*refers to a type of sweet dish that is made from various ingredients, such as semolina, flour, or nuts, and is typically sweetened with sugar or honey. It is a popular dessert in many cultures, particularly in the Middle East, South Asia, and parts of Eastern Europe*) to the visitors in accordance with their vows. After visiting the graves of the deceased and returning from the cemetery, in rural areas, people would visit the homes of those who had passed away recently, offer condolences, partake in the food offerings, and drink the sherbet (*refers to a sweet, flavored beverage typically made from fruit juices, flowers, herbs, or sugar, often diluted with water*) That evening, bonfires would again be lit in the streets, and people would chant, "Atıl-batıl (*the tossing away of bad luck*) Tuesday, may my luck open on Tuesday," and "My illness and misfortune, onto this fire!" as they jumped over the bonfires. In preparation for Novruz holiday, children would wrap old rags around the torches they had made in advance, then tightly bind them with wire, attach a long handle made of wire, and soak the torches, known as "lopa," in white oil several days before the holiday to absorb the oil. They would then set it on fire and, with all their strength, spin it into the air. As a result, the sky would be illuminated by the flying torches during the night. [5.page 148].

The celebration of Novruz holiday in different regions of Western Azerbaijan was distinguished by unique features. This distinctiveness was reflected in various elements of the holiday, including culinary preparations, games, customs, and other processes.

In the Iravan region, unlike other areas, the final night of the small Chilla was referred to as "the gathering (Jamla) falls to the ground." "Jamla" (also known as "Jamra") was one of the distinctive features of neigh-

borhood life. "Jamra" or "Jamla" was considered a symbol that represented the connection between nature and humans. In many scholarly sources, "Jamla" is considered one of the names given in popular tradition to the last four Tuesdays of the year, which are observed during the "Gray Month" leading up to Novruz holiday. The Arabic-derived word "Jamra" is used to mean "embers, warmth, or a gentle breath." Among the people of Western Azerbaijan, expressions such as "Jamla touched the air," "Jamla touched the water," "Jamla touched the earth," and "Jamla fell to the ground" are commonly used. Additionally, the Tuesdays of the period are referred to in sequence as "first Jamla," "second Jamla," "third Jamla," and "fourth Jamla." One of the ideas that suggests the "embers, warmth, or gentle breath" is associated with the time when the weather becomes somewhat milder during the Gray Month.[6].

Thus, the celebration of Novruz holiday in Western Azerbaijan, along with its important component, "Jamla" or "Jamra," was an expression of the transition from winter to spring that was unique to this land. This, in itself, is an element that reaffirms the connection of the people of Western Azerbaijan to the region, based on millennia of experience, as well as their living history and the traditions that belong to their nation.

In the Iravan region, as in other regions of Azerbaijan, on the "Last Tuesday night," girls would make wishes and go out to the doorstep. With this act, they believed that the first good or bad words they heard would reveal their future fortune and fate. Therefore, only pleasant words would be spoken in the house that evening, so that no one would hear unpleasant words when they stepped out to the doorstep. For this reason, children would often jokingly say loudly at home, "May God grant your wish!"

On the morning after the "Last Tuesday night," it was customary to go to flowing water, greet the water, jump over it three times, and then, on the way back, bring a container of that water and scatter it around the courtyard and the four corners of the house, ensuring not to spill it along the way. It is said that when someone performs these actions, the year will be favorable, and they will not experience pain or hardship. Additionally, "on the Last Tuesday night, the mouth of the flour sack would be left open so that when the blessings are distributed, a portion would be reserved for you." Or, "on the last Tuesday of the year, one should not block the flow of running water, as it would bring misfortune and cause your affairs to become tangled."

On the last Tuesday evening before Novruz holiday, after people have jumped over the bonfire as a ritual of purification, livestock, including cattle and sheep, would also be led through the fire to ensure they are not affected by negative influences associated with the Chilla period. Chilla is believed to symbolize the hardships and misfortunes of the passing year. When people and animals pass through the fire, it is thought that sorrow and worries are burned away, allowing them to emerge as if reborn.

Additionally, on the last Tuesday evening before Novruz holiday, an empty cartridge is fired from a hunting rifle as a symbolic act to break free from the negative influences of the Chilla period. It is believed

that if the rifle is not fired at that moment, one may fall under the influence of Chilla, leading to misfortune throughout the year and unsuccessful hunting.

On the evening of Novruz, each family member is given a festive share consisting of nuts, raisins, apples, tangerines, and other treats. This practice carries a symbolic meaning, and those who do not wish to take their share may pass it on to another family member or someone outside the family. Regardless of the overall abundance in the household, the portion set aside for children was always considered the sweetest. On the evening of Novruz holiday, every household prepared plov, the signature dish of the national cuisine.

Western Azerbaijanis referred to the evening of Novruz holiday as 'Kiçik Bayram' (Little Holiday) or 'Baja-baja.' (*Chimney to chimney*) One of the key traditions was sending a festive share from the parental home to children who had moved out, while also using this gesture to honor and remember elderly parents. During the festive days, it was a cherished tradition for young people, especially boys, to visit homes in pairs or small groups and drop a scarf, shawl, or hat inside as a symbolic act of gift-sharing. This practice was considered a meaningful example of communal generosity. The name 'Baja-baja' (*Chimney to Chimney*) is believed to originate from an old custom in which a shawl was lowered down through the house's chimney to receive festive offerings. At that time, it was more common for young men, especially those who were in a relationship, to symbolically throw a handkerchief into the house of the girl they wished to marry.

Not returning the handkerchief empty but instead placing festive treats inside it was a symbolic sign of the girl's acceptance of the young man's proposal. During this celebration, sending colored eggs from the bride's family to the engaged young man and the subsequent sharing of this gift among other young men held a symbolic significance. Not returning the handkerchief empty but instead placing festive treats inside it was a symbolic sign of the girl's acceptance of the young man's proposal. During this celebration, sending colored eggs from the bride's family to the engaged young man and the subsequent sharing of this gift among other young men held a symbolic significance.

Among the ancient holiday traditions, on the day of the new year's transition, people would catch small fish from the river, place them in a basin, arrange sprouted wheat (*samani*) and candles around it, and carefully observe the movements of the fish. If the fish struggled continuously or jumped out of the water, it was considered an auspicious sign, and people would celebrate the transition of the new year with applause. Following this, everyone would congratulate each other on the occasion of the holiday, marking the beginning of the community's festive celebrations. At that time, everyone considered it their duty to first congratulate the elders and respected figures of their community on the holiday. Since this day was regarded as a special one, according to tradition, people would reconcile those who were estranged.

Additionally, during Novruz holiday and other major holidays, both rural and urban populations would visit one another to exchange holiday greetings. They

would remember those they considered close, including relatives, with holiday gifts and offerings, which typically consisted of festive sweets and some form of 'khalat' (a gift or token)." During the holiday, painting red eggs, using them in a contest of strength, and the practice of winning or losing was considered one of the main traditions of Novruz holiday.

In ancient times, during holiday celebrations, traditions such as rooster fights, egg competitions, bull wrestling, and the matches between wrestlers had become customary. In the western regions of Azerbaijan, a month before the holiday, 'line hospitality' would be organized for the wrestlers, where they would be fed and given drinks in preparation for the holiday, helping them gather more strength. During the Novruz celebrations, the champion wrestler of the village, along with his team, would travel to neighboring villages for wrestling matches. During the competition, the winners would be awarded a 'namar' (a traditional prize or token)."

Since egg painting and egg fighting are among the main traditions of Novruz holiday, eggs would be dyed in every household a few days before the holiday. Typically, eggs for Novruz holiday would be dyed using red onion skins. For this purpose, a certain amount of onion peel is added to the container in which the eggs are boiled. When the boiled eggs are removed, their color, though not deep red, takes on the hue of the onion. Before the egg battle, the participants would test each other's eggs by holding their left ear with their left palm and tapping the egg in their right hand against their front teeth. This process allowed them to assess the hardness and fragility of the egg. If an agreement was reached between the participants, they would sometimes exchange their eggs. During the egg battle, if a participant's egg cracked on both the top and bottom, they were considered the loser and had to give their egg to the opponent[6].

In addition, eggs were also used in a battle format called 'train.' In this method, 15–20 eggs were lined up on the ground without being tapped against the teeth, forming a sequence. The battle process would then begin: one participant would hold an egg while the other struck it, then they would switch roles, continuing the contest in this manner. If a participant's egg cracked, it would be replaced with another. In the end, the person whose egg remained unbroken would be declared the winner and would receive all the eggs. The cost of the eggs used in the battle would be covered by the losing side. However, children were not allowed to participate in arranging the eggs in the 'train'; this was usually done by adults and young people.

During the Novruz holiday, visiting engaged girls and newlywed brides was considered a significant and essential tradition. Close female relatives from the groom's side would visit the future bride, bringing various gifts, offerings, and a decorated tray (*khoncha*), among other items. In some regions, this practice was referred to as 'galin bayramlighi' (bride's holiday celebration)[17]. In many localities, the "khoncha" would also include a Chilla watermelon, symbolizing abundance and good fortune.

Over time, numerous beliefs, superstitions, and rituals associated with Novruz holiday have emerged among people. For instance, in the Qaragoyunlu region, certain customs were practiced in connection with the last Tuesday of the year (Ilakhir Charshanba). On this day, after nightfall, individuals with a specific wish would secretly visit the doors of their relatives and neighbors, following a traditional ritual. The person would stand behind the door, place a key under their foot, and listen carefully to the conversations inside. The first word they heard was believed to indicate whether their wish would come true. If the word was associated with good fortune or a positive desire, it was considered a sign that their wish would be fulfilled. However, if the first word conveyed negativity, dissatisfaction, or concern, it was believed that achieving their desire would be difficult.

One of the traditions given special importance in the Iravan region was the 'Gurbankasma' ceremony (sacrificial ritual). In general, religious ceremonies such as 'Orujlug' and 'Maharramlik' were observed with great care and were often accompanied by ancient customs and traditions in Western Azerbaijan. During the 'Gurbankasma' ceremonies, great care was taken to follow the customs established by ancestors with strict precision. There was a belief that if the ritual was not performed accurately, the sacrifice would not be accepted. In fact, this tradition reflected the practice of an ethnic group living in a hostile environment, striving to continuously preserve and protect its existence, national, and spiritual values.

One such tradition, characteristic of the Millidara region, was the 'three Gurbankasma ceremonies. The forms of these ceremonies differed with their specific features. These included the "Bishma gurban," "Sajarası gurban," and "Niyaz gurban."

During the 'Bishma gurban' ceremony, a specially raised ram would be slaughtered. This ceremony was held in the largest house of the village, with the entire population of the village participating. The event would be led by the most respected elder or a descendant of a Seyid, who was regarded as an authority in the community. During this ceremonial process, when the sacrifice was made, its meat was not chopped; instead, the sacrificial animal would only have its joints separated. The pieces were then placed in large pots to be cooked. The meat would be cooked until it could be separated from the bones, after which it was shredded and placed into the large pots. The cooked meat was then placed between flatbread (lavaş) and distributed among the entire population of the village. Throughout the 'Bishma gurban' ceremony, prayers would be recited from the beginning to the end. In the remaining broth from the meat in the pot, cracked wheat would be added and cooked, and this cooked cracked wheat would also be distributed to the villagers. The bones of the cooked sacrifice were then wrapped in the ram's skin and buried deep in the ground in a secluded place, so that even wild animals could not find the sacred remains of the sacrifice.

During the 'Sajarası' ceremony, dough was kneaded with butter and milk, then spread out like bread inside a metal plate (saj) placed over the fire. The

dough was covered with another metal plate. Once the 'Sajarası' was cooked, it was taken off, cut into pieces, and distributed among the villagers. If those unable to slaughter an animal during the 'Bishma gurban' ceremony prepared three 'Sajarası gurbans' instead, this ritual would be considered an equivalent to the 'Bishma gurban.'

The "Niyaz gurbani" was also prepared from dough. It was slightly smaller in size than the "Sajarası gurban," with the dough kneaded with milk and a bit of sugar or honey added. The "Niyaz gurbani" was baked either on a metal plate (saj) or in a tandoor, then cut into pieces and distributed among the villagers. Often, the "Niyaz gurbani" would be baked and shared at the same time as the "Sajarası gurban." Nevertheless, the person distributing the 'Sajarası' and 'Niyaz' would give it by holding it between both hands, and the person receiving the portion would also take it with both hands, kiss it, and say, 'May Allah accept it.' When eating these portions of the sacrifice, one was required to eat carefully so that nothing would fall to the ground. To prevent the sacrifice from being considered sinful if it fell, it had to be eaten with caution. If a small piece of the sacrifice fell, it would be picked up, kissed, placed on the forehead, and then placed in a clean area, away from any dirt or contamination.

As seen from the mentioned sacrificial ceremonies, the Feast of Sacrifice (Gurban Bayram) was considered a unique celebration among the population of Western Azerbaijan, and it was greeted with respect, love, and grandeur.

One of the widely spread customs, traditions, and ceremony in the Turkic world is the 'Khidir Ellaz' ceremony. When discussing the millennia-old Novruz holiday customs and traditions of our people, it is impossible not to mention the ceremony known as 'Khidir Ilyas,' 'Khidir Ellaz,' or 'Khidir Nabi,' which was celebrated with great joy in every region, town, and village of our historic lands in Western Azerbaijan. It is stated that 'Khidir Ellaz,' as a ceremony with ancient origins, is one of the widely celebrated events among the people and is cherished and observed in the Turkic world. The "Khidir Nabi" ceremony is presented as the "protector of water, wind, and air" and is considered the equivalent of the Prophet Khidir. In ancient Turkic mythological beliefs, Khidir represents a figure who finds and drinks the water of immortality, granting eternal life and conquering death, symbolizing a being who brings life from the world of darkness. In the mythological sources of the Turkic people, Khidir is characterized as a sacred figure (wali or saint) or a guardian spirit with the status of a protector, to Yer (Earth), Su (Water), and Umay (Motherhood, childbirth, and guardianship). According to belief, if no communal feast is held in a household on 'Khidir Nabi' day, Khidir will take offense and depart, delaying the arrival of spring by obstructing its coming. In Turkic mythology, 'Khidir' is regarded as a mythical figure who embodies warmth and vitality, entering people's lives as a male hero associated with the bringing of heat and renewal.

The 'Khidir Nabi' ceremony, which is among the ancient traditions of Western Azerbaijan, has been preserved and continues to be celebrated today. Since

'Khidir Nabi' is associated with the spring season, it symbolizes the arrival of spring. By celebrating this festival, our people mark the departure of winter and the arrival of spring. On this day, the rhythm of nature manifests as the transition of seasons takes place[7].

One of the factors that preserve the traditions of our people is folk games. Like in all regions of Azerbaijan, one of the ancient folk games widely practiced in Western Azerbaijan is the 'Godu-Godu' game. During this game, people used a doll made of straw, known as 'mugavva,' which was carried in their hands. The 'Godu-Godu' folk game is considered one of the ancient folk games performed in various settlements of Azerbaijan, especially among the rural population, to stop continuous rain that would damage crops and ruin harvests. In the game, a doll is made in the form of a young bride, and, in the rain, people go door-to-door in rural areas, singing songs in praise of Godu. During this, musicians accompany the singers, and Godu is wrapped in red fabric as a symbol of the sun. The people wait for the sun to rise and the rain to stop. This can be seen as a manifestation of the ancient people's 'prayer songs' to the sun and rain in our modern life.

It should be noted that each of the 16 districts of Western Azerbaijan has its own unique wedding traditions[8.] The wedding traditions of our people living in these areas are part of a rich heritage. Although this heritage has been passed down from generation to generation, it is with regret that we acknowledge that, due to reasons related to our modernity and displacement, we are gradually losing these values or turning them into sacrifices of modernity. After the territory of Western Azerbaijan fell into the hands of the Armenians, not only our lands and monuments, but also our traditions, weddings, and folklore were severely impacted. While some of these customs, which are a part of our history, have been partially forgotten, we must strive to preserve and revive them in some way.

In the settlements of Western Azerbaijan, the traditions of our ancestors, as well as the customs and celebrations of the elders, were carried out beautifully, including weddings. During this time, wool was spun and quilts and mattresses were prepared as part of the dowry for the bride, while receiving blessings from the village elders until everything was ready[9]. Just as in other places, one of the ancient customs and foundations of our traditions in the lands of Western Azerbaijan was that the beginning of a wedding would bring joy to the community: "All the work done during the wedding would take place with the blessings of the elders and wise women. Before the wedding festivities, there were distinct matchmaking customs in the territory of Western Azerbaijan. As parents would advise, they would say, 'Go to that person's house and bring a black stone to place in our yard, and we'll see if it will bring good fortune or not.'" If everything went smoothly and in order within 10 to 15 days, it was then believed that everything would turn out well.

In Western Azerbaijan, due to the harsh winter season and the early onset of cold weather in certain areas, weddings were primarily held during the summer months. Each settlement and village would typically host 5 to 10 weddings throughout the year, especially

during the summer period. Wedding ceremonies were planned from the beginning of spring, and the families preparing for the wedding would mutually agree on a rotation system, with one wedding taking place every Saturday and Sunday. In this way, all weddings held during this period would be open to everyone's invitation. Even if the wedding host had a disagreement with someone, that person and their family would still be invited to the wedding. Whether to accept the invitation or not was considered a personal choice for the family members. In other words, not inviting someone, being excluded from the invitation, or not attending the wedding would be considered a great disrespect. Weddings would last for 2-3 days: Friday, Saturday, and Sunday. A day or two before the wedding, relatives, friends, and neighbors would gather to bake the wedding bread and prepare for the event.

In the Zangazur region, marriages were mainly based on the mutual love of the young couple, with the wishes of the parents considered in rare cases. After the young man obtained the girl's consent through a close acquaintance, he would convey his 'concern' or 'intentions' to his mother through his sister or friends. For this reason, the boy's mother or sister would go to the girl's house for a 'wall conversation,' and after the boy's intentions were conveyed to the girl's family, a few days later, the boy's mother would visit the bride's paternal home to seek the approval of the girl's mother. Once consent was given, the next step would be the commencement of the 'matchmaking' process [9].

For the 'matchmaking' process, the boy's father and mother, uncles or aunts, and the elders of the family would go. Around 10 people from each side would participate in this event. According to ancient tradition, a headscarf would be brought to the matchmaking. If an agreement was reached, the boy's mother would place the headscarf on the future bride's head. In the modern era, during the matchmaking process, a headscarf or a thin ring is brought. The conversation during the matchmaking is often a mix of humor and seriousness, with the use of proverbs and sayings. In cases where an agreement is not reached, the tone of the conversation would be carefully chosen in advance to avoid any awkwardness.

The matchmaking ceremony would begin with the tea ceremony. The host would bring tea to the table, but the guests would not reach for the tea immediately. To create a pleasant atmosphere, the conversation would be framed with phrases such as 'May what has come to our tea and bread also come to our bride' and others, in an effort to establish a positive and warm tone in the gathering. During the conversation, the elder from the bride's family would say, 'May God bless, may you speak sweetly,' after which sweet tea would be served. According to the wise women, the tea served at the table had to be prepared in such a way that the color of the brew would float on top of the clear water, and after sugar was added to the cup, it should be stirred. This was symbolic of unity and coming together. After the tea ceremony, food and drinks would be brought to the table. During this time, all the expenses of the matchmaking would be covered by the bride's family.

After the matchmaking, according to tradition, the 'engagement ceremony' would take place. The expenses of the engagement were typically covered by the boy's family, not in cash, but in kind. During the engagement ceremony, the girl's engagement ring, other jewelry, clothes needed for the bride, sweets, and specially prepared gift trays would be brought from the boy's house to the girl's house with the participation of the boy's close relatives. During the engagement, shoes were not brought to avoid any discomfort or shortage. Among the engagement expenses paid in kind, onions were not included to avoid any unpleasantness. The girl's family would invite guests to the 'engagement ceremony,' gathering all the young women and brides of the village. Each family attending the event would bring a 'tray,' which would contain sweets, fabric, clothes for the bride, perfume, and other items. The engagement ceremony would take place under the sounds of pleasant music. If it was not possible to invite musicians due to financial constraints or other reasons, a tape recorder or phonograph would be used to carry out this joyous occasion [9].

During the engagement process, the future groom would participate along with his close friends, and according to traditional customs, one of the women from the boy's family would place the engagement ring on the girl's finger. A while after the engagement process, the boy, accompanied by one or two close friends, would visit the girl's house for an introductory visit, provided they had given prior notice.

Before the traditions of 'soz kasdi' (finalizing the agreement) and 'paltar bichdi' (clothing preparation) were carried out in the settlements of Western Azerbaijan, the elders from both the boy's and girl's families would sit together and reach an agreement known as 'kharj-khorak' (cost and provisions). Once this agreement was made, the 'wedding bread' would be baked, the 'wedding tent' would be set up, and the 'wedding henna' would be prepared. On the first night of the wedding, the 'henna ceremony' would take place. During the wedding process, the 'abduction of the groom,' the 'bringing of the bride,' the 'wedding feast,' the 'tray evening,' the preparation of the 'shah' for the bride and groom, the singing of wedding songs, and other customs were carried out as key elements of the Western Zangazur wedding tradition [9].

In Western Azerbaijan, on Saturday morning, close relatives and selected individuals from the boy's family would go to the girl's house for the 'clothing preparation' ceremony. There, a gathering would be held, and the guests from the boy's side would be served 'wedding bread.' This tradition would replace the girl's wedding, and only women and young girls would participate in the gathering. The cost of the gathering held at the girl's house would be covered by the boy's family. Towards the evening, the boy's family would bring henna for the bride. Before going to bring the bride on Sunday, the groom and his close relatives would be praised in a tent set up at the boy's house. With these praises, musicians would collect contributions from the groom's relatives and close associates. The verses of the praise and their delivery would be chosen according to the familial status of the relative:

father, mother, uncle, paternal uncle, aunt, maternal aunt, etc. For example:

“It would be better if the sweet pomegranate's
bitterness,

Let the boy's sister bring the contributions”

Typically, the praise would be performed by either a minstrel or a singer."

In this way, the diversity and richness of wedding customs and traditions in Western Azerbaijan were passed down from generation to generation. During the 'henna night' ceremony, girls would sing special songs. The main songs performed were 'nanaylar'. In the Agbaba region of Western Azerbaijan, one of the characteristic ceremonies of the henna night was considered to be the singing of the 'nanaylar'.

“Oh Henna, Henna, Henna,

Either the groom will take you, or the khan will,
Henna.

The barley lake is serene, its waters very deep,
Either your eyes are gentle, or your gentle eyes.

Oh Henna, Henna, Henna,

Either the groom will take you, or the khan will,
Henna”[9].

In modern-day weddings, it is customary to spin the bride around the lamp. However, in the traditional weddings of Western Azerbaijan, the bride would be spun around either the hearth or the oven. This symbolized the bride receiving blessings from her parental home and carrying the hearth to her new home. From the beginning to the end of the wedding, the bride's face would be covered with a veil so that no one could see her face on the wedding day. When leaving her parental home, the bride would take with her bread, a trunk, and, along with them, a pot of halva. This custom was considered a symbol of sweetness.

In the modern era, the tradition of tying the bride's waist with a red ribbon is carried out by the groom's older brother, whereas in Western Azerbaijan, this tradition was performed by the bride's older brother. Today, these customs have slightly changed. Additionally, according to tradition, when the bride leaves her parental home, they would tie money in her hand, symbolizing that the bride is bringing prosperity and abundance to the hearth (home) she is moving to.

When the bride was taken, musicians, and in some places, trumpet (zurna-zourna) players, would play a melancholic tune, which would move the mother to tears as she parted from her daughter. Among the traditions of the people of Western Azerbaijan, the custom of the groom throwing an apple on the bride's head is still preserved in some regions, especially in Nakhchivan. On the wedding day, as the bride was leaving her home, the groom would climb to the roof and throw an apple on her head. To prevent any harm or injury to the bride, a "sini" (protective tray) would be held above her head. The reason behind the groom throwing an apple on the bride's head was believed to bring prosperity and abundance to the household she was joining. Additionally, it was believed that the children the bride would bear would be fortunate and bring good fortune to the family [9]. In ancient Turkish mythology, the apple symbolizes several meanings, including the symbol of wholeness. It is believed that in order for the newly

formed family to be long-lasting and whole, the tradition of throwing an apple on the bride's head, which has been passed down from our ancestors, is still preserved today.

In addition, in the weddings of Western Azerbaijan, the bride, groom, best man, and maid of honor all had special attire to stand out from the others. Even the horse that carried the bride was adorned, with a white ribbon tied around its neck. In traditional weddings, women's clothing was also distinct, with women wearing a veil over their faces. When the bride was taken out of her house for the wedding, the imam would come to perform the marriage ceremony. As soon as the imam left the house, musicians would begin to play slow, melancholic music, creating an atmosphere that would cause the bride's mother to become emotional and cry. These tears were considered to carry a positive and meaningful connotation[10].

In the past, the groom's family would sometimes bring the bride from distant regions. During those times, as the horse played a key role as a mode of transportation, the bride would be brought to the groom's house on horseback[12].

According to Turkish traditions, taking the bride on horseback was considered an ancient custom. When traveling from the bride's house to the groom's house, there would be attendants who would accompany the bride on horseback. There was a saying that "the one who rode the horse quickly would be given money and rewards. At this time, the children of the village would climb the mountains or high places to see whose horse would reach the groom's house first. Most of the time, engaged girls would go to high places to watch the horse riders, hoping to see that their fiancé could ride faster than the others and surpass them all[10].

In addition, on the wedding day, a "joy pillow" would be given to the horse riders. The confident young rider, as soon as he received the pillow, would not give it to anyone and would try to quickly deliver it to the groom's house in a short time. The meaning behind this was to signal that the bride was about to arrive at the groom's house. The young rider who rode the horse would receive a reward (*nəmər*) from the groom's family for bringing this joyful news. When the bride approached the groom's house, she would dismount from the horse, take off her shoes, and enter her new home barefoot. The symbolic meaning of this action was that the removal of her shoes represented the desire to avoid any hardship, as shoes, in traditional customs, were associated with tightness or difficulty. This action conveyed the message that the bride wished to bring happiness to her new family, to ensure a prosperous life for them, and to avoid bringing any misfortune.

After this, when the bride arrived at the door, lavash (flatbreads) and candies were laid out in front of her. The bride would pick up the lavash one by one, place them on her left arm, and then start collecting the candies from the ground. This action symbolized that the bride was bringing prosperity and sweetness to the house. The lavash represented abundance, while the candies symbolized sweetness, and it was believed that this tradition laid the foundation for happiness in the new home.

The "Shah Bazama" (King's Decoration) tradition in Western Azerbaijan is also known as the deposing of the king. The roots of this tradition date back to the XVII century. After the wedding in Western Azerbaijan, the groom had to visit the homes of the best man and the maid of honor, where a Shah was to be decorated in honor of the bride and groom. The symbolic meaning of this was that a Shah, made from tree branches about one meter in height, was decorated with various sweets, dishes, seasonal fruits, chocolates, and various candies. As a result, the Shah became so heavy that its weight reached up to 40-50 kilograms. Additionally, a cooked rooster would be placed on top of the Shah. This also had its own symbolic meaning. At this point, competition would arise between the best man and the maid of honor regarding the *nəmər* (reward), based on their roles in the ceremony [9]. When the Shah was brought into the newlyweds' room, tradition dictated that only the newlyweds could take sweets from the decorated Shah. During this time, the family members of the house would specially guard the Shah to ensure that no one took any sweets or candies from it. When the Shah was brought into the house, the people from the bride's family would come to the bride's room, holding candles in their hands, following the Shah.

After the bride arrived at the groom's house, it was a must for her father-in-law to come and say, "Oh, bride, sit down, I will give you a cow." Only after this would the bride sit down. In the villages of Western Azerbaijan, particularly in Goycha, once the wedding day was set, the musicians would start playing wedding songs from one end of the village, gathering neighbors and relatives along the way. They would continue playing and dancing until they reached the end of the village. During this time, musicians would be given a share or money. The arrival of the bards was the highlight of the wedding. As soon as the bards arrived at the wedding, both young and old, girls and brides, would gather around the tent to watch the celebration. In weddings, it was one of the essential traditions for the bards to offer blessings and recite traditional songs or "ustadnamalar" (masterpieces of poetry).

For this reason, weddings in Western Azerbaijan could not proceed without the bards. One of the most interesting aspects was that, along with the bard, members of the community would also engage in storytelling and oral poetry, known as (*dastans*). There were even weddings where these exchanges and stories could last for 4-5 days. The hosts of the wedding would continue the celebration until the story was completed. As a result, by the end of the gathering, a feast would be laid out.

It should be noted that the traditional "yalli" dance, which is specifically performed at weddings in Western Azerbaijan, continues to be a part of modern celebrations. In fact, the "yalli" dance is considered one of the distinctive features of weddings in Western Azerbaijan[9]. At the wedding gathering, everyone had their own distinct dance rhythm and specific type of dance. The main highlight of the wedding, however, was the "yalli" dance. The eldest member of the hosting family would start the first "yalli" dance, holding a handkerchief and leading the dance. Then, children, sons,

daughters, brides, and young people would join in. This dance, a symbol of unity and solidarity for the Turkish people, was joyfully performed by everyone. Each region's "yalli" had its own distinctive dance elements. At weddings, "yalli" was often performed with linked arms. Everyone who participated in this dance expressed their sincerity, joy, and national pride to the newlyweds and their community.

One of the customs in our weddings was the "kidnapping of the groom." During this time, the main responsibility and care fell on the best man and the maid of honor. Relatives would try to distract those protecting the groom in order to abduct him. If the groom was kidnapped, the best man and maid of honor would face consequences. According to tradition, during the "kidnapping," the groom was not allowed to resist. In such cases, those who "kidnapped the groom" could demand that the wedding continue at the house where the groom was being held. Sometimes, even the bride's friends would deceive and kidnap the groom. At this point, they would only release him after receiving a gift from the groom's mother. The following day, the best man and maid of honor were required to slaughter a lamb and host a feast for those who had kidnapped the groom.

In the past, during weddings, sweets were sprinkled on the groom and bride's heads to symbolize sweetness. According to these traditions, when the bride left her house, throwing candies behind her was a symbolic act meant to bring abundance and prosperity to the household she was moving to [9]. However, nowadays, this tradition is rarely encountered. During the wedding celebration, the groom would not sit for long in the tent. During the "baytarifi" (groom's praise) and "bayoyatma" (groom's entrance) ceremonies, the groom would enter the wedding tent with his best man and second man. The bride, on the other hand, would generally remain unseen during the celebration, and she would be brought from her father's house to the groom's house. A white veil would be placed over her face, and on top of it, a red cloth would be added. This was done to protect the bride from evil spirits and the "evil eye" due to her beauty and transformation on her wedding day. This custom, which originates from ancient Turkic shamanistic traditions, is now only preserved and followed in some remote areas. Additionally, as soon as the bride entered the house, she would break a plate under her feet to scare away evil spirits and avoid misfortune. This was done because the bride arrived in the evening, when the darkness and evil spirits began to emerge, and thus, scaring away these spirits was considered essential. Along with this, when the bride was brought into the house, a young boy would be placed in her arms to ensure that the first child of the newlyweds would be a boy. In the community, the "boy" was considered both the continuation of the family lineage and a symbol of protection against enemies. One of the traditional practices performed for prosperity and fertility of the house was to dip the bride's hand in honey and rub it on the threshold, cut bread over her head, and place rice in her palm [17].

In this article, alongside the national and seasonal holiday of Novruz, we have attempted to highlight the distinctiveness of the wedding ceremonies among the

people of Western Azerbaijan, ranging from the bride price ceremony to the final phase of the wedding, the groom's ceremony. At the same time, the specific features of religious holidays and popular folk games widely practiced among the people were also discussed to some extent. It is not possible to present all the characteristic customs and traditions specific to the people of Western Azerbaijan in detail within one article. However, by presenting these customs and traditions in general, we aimed to convey that the people of Western Azerbaijan have an ancient worldview. We would like to unequivocally state that "a people with national customs and traditions is truly ancient."

Conclusions. The study of historical and cultural heritage based on ancient traditions has, in itself, been shaped and brought to life as a result of the rich material and spiritual cultural examples that have emerged over millennia in the regions of Western Azerbaijan, including Iravan, Goycha, Zangazur, and Daralayaz. According to researchers, cities such as Iravan, Vedibasar, Zangazur, Daralayaz, Aghbaba, Shorayel, Lori, Pambak, Goycha, Garagoyunlu, and Shamshaddin are all territories of Western Azerbaijan, and these regions have been closely interconnected with other areas. The fact that the customs, traditions, and daily life of the Turks living in the regions of Shamshaddin, Garagoyunlu, Dilijan, and Goycha were almost identical to those of the local population of Ganjabasar is one of the historical facts [10]. One of the most important goals that each of us sets before ourselves as a duty is to preserve and pass down our national customs and traditions that have lasted for centuries. Anyone who wishes to sustain a nation must, first and foremost, consider it their responsibility to transmit its customs and traditions to future generations and to incorporate them into daily life, even as they modernize over time.

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